

The Effect of Compensation and Intrinsic Motivation on Organizational Motivation and Turnover Intentions Lecturer (Study on Foundation Lecturers at Private Universities in Indonesia's South Sulawesi)

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Abstract:- This study aimed to analyze the effect of compensation and intrinsic motivation on organizational commitment and turnover intentions of foundation lecturers at private universities in South Sulawesi after Covid-19. This is quantitative research with survey method. The questionnaire distributed was 255 copies, but respondents who filled out the questionnaire were 98 foundation lecturers at various universities swasta in South Sulawesi Province so that the sample of this study was 98 responses. Data analysis using *generalized structured compound analysis* (GSCA). From the results of the study, four variables that affect significant and one variable whose influence is not significant. Compensation variables have a significant effect on organizational commitment. Compensation has no significant effect on turnover intentions. Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment. Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on turnover intentions. Organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intentions.

Keywords:- Compensation, intrinsic motivation, organizational competence, and intention to change lecturers after covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

For two years, the COVID-19 pandemic has hit the world community both in developed and developing countries, including Indonesia, which has had a broad impact on people's lives, including social and economic interactions. In addition, changing the learning system from face-to-face learning to online learning. In this regard, Hendra Achmadi, et al., (2022) found that during the pandemic, self-efficacy and e-service play an important role in the success of online learning programs. Therefore, universities must increase self-efficacy and e-service for the success of online learning. Covid-19 has also affected business performance, resulting in many small and medium businesses going out of business and many employees being laid off, which has an impact on the decline in the community's economy. Economic recovery during the pandemic, the government must do it in various precise ways so that the Indonesian economy can return to normal. Research by RahmaWahdiniwatyat., al (2022) found that economic recovery solutions need to collaborate Quadruple Helix and refer to processes, structures, inputs, and outputs. Businesspeople must adapt to digital technology to market

their products in the midst of fierce competition. Chrisanty V. Layman (2022) found that digital marketing adaptation has a positive effect on competition during the COVID-19 pandemic. The sluggish economy during the Covid-19 period has resulted in many companies reducing their workforce so that it can increase unemployment which has an impact on high education performance. One of the effects is the decline in the number of students due to the termination of employment which causes many families to delay entering their children to continue their studies at university, thus affecting the compensation system. However, we should be grateful because at the beginning of 2022 covid-19 gradually left the earth of Indonesia because the Indonesian government requires all people to be vaccinated so that people exposed to covid gradually recover and the number of people affected by the covid-19 virus decreases. Although the situation has improved, new students have not experienced a significant increase so that lecturer compensation at several private universities has not been stable after covid.

Compensation can increase work motivation, (Mathis & Jackson, 2002). If compensation matches expectations and workload can increase intrinsic motivation. Research by SaparuddinMughtarat., al (2018) found that compensation has a significant effect on intrinsic motivation. To increase intellectual motivation among employees, organizational leaders need to improve the compensation system so as to increase organizational commitment. Faisal Almadiat., al (2017); SusetyoDarmanto (2020) found that motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment (affective, continuence and normative commitment). To increase organizational commitment, the Rector and Chairman of the foundation need to design a compensation system. A Nur Insan and Muhammad Isa Ansari (2022) found that compensation has asignificant influence onorganizational co-mitmen. Leaders build organizational commitment and nourish the work environment so as to minimize turnover intentions. Lisnatiawati, Saragih and DjamareIHermanto (2022) found asignificant nurturing work environment with turnover intentions. If an organization's work environment is unhealthy and compensation is low, it can increase turnover intentions. DzulfiqarMudhoffarSiregar and Tri Maryati (2020) found that compensation has a significant effect on turnover intentions. Some foundation lecturers at private universities moved to teach to other universities due to low comparison.

Compensation in some private universities post-covid is still unstable because for two years private universities have experienced a decrease in the number of students. The increase in new students in higher education has an effect on reducing the classes taught, thus affecting the compensation of lecturers. If lecturers teach more than three classes, they get a teaching honor, but during the COVID-19 pandemic, the classes taught decreased because the number of students decreased so that the milk they received decreased. In this case, the participation of the leader (Rector) is needed to motivate lecturers to increase organizational commitment. Qëndrimbytyqi (2020) found motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment. To maintain organizational commitment, a good compensation system is needed. I Gede Riana (2016); Novianto Arie and Budiono Nur Aktif (2020) found that compensation has a significant effect on organizational commitment. However, research by Nadia Nurfarida et al. (2018) found that the composition of her influence was not significant with organizational commitment. The two research results are different so there is a gap. Based on the gap, researchers are interested in examining the effect of compensation and intrinsic motivation on organizational commitment and turnover intentions.

Organizational commitment is the loyalty and attachment of employees to the organization, which plays an important role in work. For example, employees who have high organizational commitment will have lower absenteeism rates and are less likely to leave the organization, compared to employees who have low organizational commitment. To maintain organizational commitment, not young people need an accurate strategy by giving employees rights so that they are motivated to work.

Organizational commitment is associated with turnover intentions. Dinar Hendrayani (2013) found organizational commitment to significantly affect turnover intentions. This shows that if the organizational committee of high lecturers they persist to continue teaching at the university where they teach and do not think about transferring to another university. In this case, the participation of leaders is needed to maintain organizational commitment in order to improve the work performance of lecturers. Research by Sri Ramadhani Asda and Medina Nilasari (2022) found that authentic leadership participation can improve job performance and increase employee attachment to work. In addition, the leader (Rector) needs to improve the compensation system in order to minimize turnover intentions. by Naidu and Satyanarayana (2018); Nadia Nurfadilah et al. (2018) found that compensation has a significant effect on Turnover Intentions. With a good compensation system, it can minimize the desire of lecturers to move to other universities.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Compensation is an incentive given to employees for their hard work as a right to the results of their work that has been done well and quality. In practice, compensation must still be given to employees due to the law. There may be employees whose performance does not meet expectations

but they are still paid due to applicable laws and regulations. Compensation is a strategy to retain employees who have high competence, (Yokohama, 2007). However, in practice, many things are taken into consideration in providing compensation. One of them is the ability of the organization to provide compensation in accordance with market demands on the salaries of employees with high abilities. In this regard, organization is guided to be able to operate effectively and efficiently and is important to obtain human resources who have quality competencies. Good compensation is a combination of financial and non-financial rewards, (Gberevbie, 2011).

Compensation is viewed from the perspective of rewards, recognition and rewards in the form of base salary and incentives. Compensation can increase work motivation, (Mathis & Jackson, 2002). Compensation by better entrepreneurial-oriented organizations tends to base payments tied to market-accepted compensation standards rather than internal equity issues. One way to retain employees who have competence is to provide compensation in accordance with their skills so that they are motivated to work. In this case the organization needs strong financial support so that it is sufficient to provide incentives for employees and encourage them to stay in the organization.

Compensation provides satisfaction to employees so that the organization can be ensured to run on the right track to achieve goals. Conversely, if the organization cannot provide adequate and satisfactory compensation, the organization faces a vulnerability in maintaining competent human resources. For this reason, compensation needs to be managed properly and needs to be analyzed comprehensively. There are seven indicators of lecturer compensation, namely salary, functional allowances, structural allowances for those in their positions, lecturer certification, teaching honors, food fees, transportation fees. If the compensation system in the organization is good, it can increase intrinsic motivation.

A. *Intrinsic motivation*

Motivation is defined as "A physiological concept related to strength and direction of behavior" (Torington and Hall 1991). This shows that individuals who have high intrinsic motivation are seen in their attitude towards work. Motivation is the desire from within the individual to contribute to the achievement of organizational goals so that the personal goals of the members of the organization are also achieved. The two-factor theory of motivation explains that there is intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation comes from within each person which influences one's thoughts and behavior. While extrinsic motivation is an external factor determined by the leader of the organization in the form of salary, working conditions, organizational policies and labor relations such as rewards and promotions or structural positions, (Herzberg, et al, 2003). There are twelve indicators of intrinsic activation m, namely: 1). Encouragement to be responsible for work. 2). Takerisks. 3). higher achievers. 4). social interaction. 5). try to work together in completing the job. 6). trying to gain recognition of abilities. 7). Bmeansndak sportsmanship in

work. 8). Challenging work. 9). safety at work. 10). freedom of work/not under pressure. 11). The institution entrusts employees to work well. 12). get respect from colleagues. Intrinsic motivation has to do with compensation. If compensation matches expectations, expectations and workload can increase organizational commitment.

B. Organizational Commitment

Commitment is defined as "an employee level of attachment to some aspect of work", (Allen and Meyer 1993) That is, organizational commitment is an employee bond to work and the organization. In addition, organizational commitment is employee loyalty. Luthans, (2001; 235) explains that organizational commitment is a dimension to assess the survivability of employees in working for the organization. Meyer, (1991; Luthans, 2001; 237; Meyer, *et al*, 2002; Coetzee, 2005) explained that there are three dimensions of commitment, namely 1) emotional attachment of employees to the organization / affective commitment. 2). The employee must bear the costs if he leaves the organization/continuence committee. 3). Must persist to keep working on the organization/normative commitment. Organizational commitment has two basic dimensions: (a) it characterizes the employee's relationship in the organization; b) it has implication for decision to continue or stop membership in the organizational, (Meyer and Allen, 1991). This means that organizational commitment is a condition that determines the employee's continued relationship with the organization and implications for the decision to stay or leave the organization. In the organizational commitment variable, there are three dimensions and six indicators, namely: the affective commitment dimension, with an indicator of 1). Employees boast the company to others. 2) Employees feel involved in the organization. In the dimension of continuence commitment there are two indicators, namely: 1). Employees stay at the company because the rewards match the workload. 2). Career is in line with expectations. While the normative commitment dimension has two indicators: 1). Employees carry out their duties well in various organizations. 2). Employees are obliged to stay at work. Organizational commitment is related to turnover intentions. Research by Dinar Hendrayani (1013) found that organizational commitment has a significant impact on turnover intentions.

C. Turnover intention

Mathis and Jackson (2008: 84) Turnover is a process by which employees leave the organization / company and must be replaced by other employees. Meanwhile, according to Mobley *et al* quoted by Khikmawati, (2015) turnover intentions are the intention of employees to stop working from their jobs voluntarily or move from one company to another company of their own choosing. Turnover intentions are the desire of employees to leave the organization / company, with various reasons that cause turnover intentions including the desire to get a better job. According to Mobley *et al* (cited by Halimah *et al*, 2016) there are three indicators of turnover measurement, namely: (1) Thinking of Quitting: Starting with job dissatisfaction felt by employees,

(2) Intention to search for alternatives, individuals wanting to find work in other organizations. (3) Intention to quit: individuals who intend to quit if they get a better job.

III. HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Compensation affects organizational commitment

The fact shows that all people who work are based on the motive to get compensation in the form of compensation for the work they have done. If the rewards are inline with expectations and can meet all their needs, employees will feel satisfied and comfortable to work in the organization and will not think about leaving the organization. Thus, compensation is one of the factors that trigger organisational commitment. Research on the effect of compensation on organizational commitment has been conducted by I Gede Riana & I Wayan Pradnyantha Wirasedana, (2016) and proves that compensation has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Age and gender are often determinants of organizational commitment. Employees over the age of 40 years have high organizational commitment because they are less likely to be accepted in other companies.

B. Compensation affects turnover intention

It has been made clear that compensation will be a trigger for organizational commitment. If organizational commitment is high, employees are reluctant to leave the organization, thus minimizing turnover intentions. Thus, compensation will be an impetus for someone to keep working for the organization. Research Nadia Nurfadilah *et.*, *al* (2018); Dzulfiqar Mudhoffar Siregar and Tri Maryati (2021) found that compensation has a significant effect on turnover intentions. This shows that compensation needs attention for every organizational leader to compensate for the workload so that employees do not think about moving to another organization.

C. Intrinsic motivation influences organizational commitment

As we know that motivation is the impulse from within each individual to do something that affects one's thoughts and behavior. Research Faisal N. Al-madi *et.*, *al* (2017); Qëndrim Bytyqi (2020) found that intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment (affective commitment, continuence commitment and normative commitment). This can be interpreted that if a person's motivation is high, organizational commitment is also high. Likewise, if a person's motivation is low, organizational commitment is also low because of the low desire to do work so that they are not committed to staying in an organization. This is related to compensation.

D. Motivasi intrinsic berpengaruh terhadap niat turnover

The fact shows that intrinsic motivation is an internal motivation to do something. However, if employees experience low job satisfaction such as minimal salary and an organizational environment that is not conducive, they are motivated to move to another organization. Research by Jafar Husain *et.*, *al* (2018) found significant motivation for employee turnover intentions and performance.

E. Organizational commitment affects turnover intentions

A person who has a high organizational commitment will certainly try his best to support the organization. The support can be in the form of support to carry out the best possible work. Prioritize the interests of the organization over personal interests and support every policy and atmosphere owned by the organization. This is very clear if a person who has high organizational commitment does not think about leaving the organization. Research by Dinar Hendrayani (1013) found that organizational commitment has a significant impact on turnover intentions.

The conceptual framework of this study is based on Thomson & Rampton's reward theory, (2003) that companies compensate employees to feel satisfied and perform well rather than just giving annual bonuses. Maund, (2001) explained that in order for employees to be motivated to work they need to be given financial and non-financial awards in the form of salary and praise.

Compensation is an important factor to motivate employees so that they stay with the organization. Proper compensation is a combination of financial in the form of money and non-financial praise so that employees can perform well, (Gberevbie, 2011). Compensation is a reward given to employees for the results of their work that aims to motivate employees which can further influence increasing organizational commitment.

Compensation needs to consider workload, skills and competencies. One factor that can increase the motivation of a worker is compensation, (Mathis & Jackson, 2002). Compensation is a reward given to employees for the results of their work which aims to motivate employees which can further affect employee performance. Research by Tahmem Siddiqi & Sadia (2018) found that compensation and motivation have an effect on employee performance. Furthermore, draw the conceptual framework of the research as follows:

Gambar 1: Model Penelitian

The hypothesis proposed is as follows:

- H1: Compensation has a significant effect on organizational commitment
- H2: Compensation has a significant effect on turnover intentions.
- H3: Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment
- H4: Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on turnover intentions
- H5: Organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intentions

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is quantitative with survey methods by circulating questionnaires prepared to obtain responses to the variables in this study. The questionnaire was distributed to foundation lecturers at Fajar University, Nitro Finance College, East Indonesia University, Darma Nusa High School, Andi Jemma Palopo University. The exogenous variables in this study were compensation and intrinsic motivation. While endogenous variables are

organizational commitment and turnover intentions. The questionnaires were distributed as many as 225, but only 98 returned so that the research sample was 98 lecturers. The Likert scale used in this study is: (1) strongly disagree (2) disagree (3) neutral / undecided. (4) agree (5) strongly agree. After the data is obtained, the data is analyzed using statistics with general structured component analysis analysis. Reliability tests are used to minimize the concept of bias in the consistency of measuring instruments used, (Sekaran, 2006). The sample of this study is lecturers at several private universities in South Sulawesi Province. The criteria for lecturers given questionnaires are as follows: (1) lecturers who have a service period of more than ten years. (2) Lecturers who have a certificate of educators. Demographically, the sample of this study can be described as follows: The respondents of this study were dominated by 55 male respondents or 56% and women 23 people or 44%. Respondents ranged in age from 41 – 50 years. The work experience of a respondent was about >20 years. The full demographics of respondents are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Respondent Demography

Atributes	Item	F	%
Gender	Men	55	56%
	Women	43	44%
Age (Years)	21 – 30 years	20	20%
	31 – 40 years	29	30%
	41 – 50 years	37	38%
	>50 years	12	12%
Work Experiences	1 – 10 years	26	26%
	11 – 20 years	33	34%
	>20 years	39	40%

The primary data in this study are data obtained directly from respondents by distributing questionnaires regarding compensation, intrinsic motivation, organizational commitment and lecturer turnover intentions. While the secondary data of this research was collected from research sources in the form of lecturer data at various universities. This study uses a Likert scale, namely: strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral / doubtful (3), agree (4) strongly agree (5). After the data is obtained, the data is analyzed using statistics with general structured component analysis analysis. Validity tests are carried out with the aim of obtaining precision and accuracy. Reliability tests are used to minimize the concept of bias in the consistency of measuring instruments used, (Sekaran, 2006). In hypothesis testing, this study was carried out by looking at the value of the probability, where the p-value with an alpha of 5% is less than 0.05. Then the t-table value for 5% alpha is 1.96. So that with these criteria for imagining or rejecting the Hypothesis, namely H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected when the t-statistic > 1.96 , in addition to rejecting / accepting the Hypothesis using probability, H_a is accepted if $p < 0.05$.

V. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Measurement Model

The construct validity & reliability test is an assessment of the outer model. All variables are analyzed based on the reliability of each convergent indicator.

FIT	0.357101
AFIT	0.341716
FITs	0.319452

$$FIT = 0.357$$

FIT shows the total variance of all variables that can be explained by a given model. FIT values range from 0 to 1. So, the model formed can explain all existing variables by 0.35. Compensation, Organizational Commitment, Intrinsic Motivation and turnover intentions that can be explained by the model are 35.0% and the rest (65.0%) can be explained by other variables.

$$AFIT = 0.341$$

AFIT (Adjusted FIT) is similar to R squared adjusted in regression analysis. AFIT can be used for model comparison. The model with the largest value AFIT can be selected among the better models. The diversity that can be explained by the model is 34.1 % .

Table 1: Measurement Model

Loadings				
	Estimate	SE	95% CI(L)	95% CI(U)
Kompensasi				
X.1.1	0.775948	0.047054	0.674386	0.849772
X.1.2	0.73013	0.048874	0.62932	0.827924
X.1.3	0.641634	0.08454	0.464264	0.793708
X.1.4	0.604054	0.080418	0.445794	0.76856
X.1.5	-0.46652	0.089604	-0.63204	-0.25685
X.1.6	0.739157	0.056016	0.601753	0.82453
X.1.7	0.743525	0.047141	0.635495	0.811645
Motivasi intrinsik				
X.2.1	0.567906	0.126106	0.319095	0.803254
X.2.2	0.519803	0.118647	0.238251	0.699091
X.2.3	0.191492	0.269084	-0.37563	0.706285
X.2.4	-0.1322	0.269955	-0.55904	0.43021
X.2.5	-0.12592	0.234629	-0.52484	0.495058
X.2.6	0.381617	0.161708	0.04756	0.651827
X.2.7	0.441483	0.133785	0.130797	0.635202
X.2.8	0.277132	0.164332	-0.09867	0.568557
X.2.9	0.247219	0.202614	-0.29247	0.535011

X.2.10	0.488748	0.123728	0.179575	0.642475
X.2.11	0.574734	0.134113	0.154557	0.756326
X.2.12	-0.30262	0.23764	-0.62637	0.288546
X.2.13	0.287398	0.220274	-0.17647	0.588257
X.2.14	0.717326	0.087356	0.495482	0.807834
X.2.15	0.416949	0.201729	-0.07817	0.674424
Komitmenorganisasional				
Y.1.1	0.836971	0.038514	0.747296	0.89761
Y.1.2	0.781483	0.056531	0.61603	0.859515
Y.1.3	0.994765	0.044433	0.863967	0.999967
Y.1.4	0.140673	0.351186	-0.55616	0.678204
Y.1.5	0.823325	0.030873	0.776442	0.88745
Y.1.6	0.818129	0.044435	0.691359	0.882011
Turnover intention				
Y.2.1	0.822313	0.038184	0.747129	0.885881
Y.2.2	0.712583	0.091878	0.495592	0.836386
Y.2.3	0.824854	0.029533	0.766752	0.885214

➤ *Compensation Variables*

There are seven indicators that influence the formation of variables, where all indicators are significant to measure variables. When viewed from the *estimatevalue onloadings* obtained for each indicator, indicator X.1.1 is the one that best describes the Compensation variable. The *estimated* value of this indicator is the largest among the other seven indikator, which is 0.77.

➤ *Intrinsic Motivation Variables:*

There are fifteen indicators that influence the formation of variables, where all indicators are significant for measuring variables. When viewed from the *estimatevalue onloadings* obtained for each indicator, indicator X.2.14 is the one that best describes the variable Intrinsic Motivation. The estimated value of this indicator is the largest among the other five indikator, which is 0.71.

➤ *Organizational committee variables:*

There are three variables of commitment and six indicators that influence the formation of variables, all of which are significant indicators to measure variables. When viewed from the *estimatevalue onloadings* obtained for each indicator, indicator Y.1.3 is the one that best describes the variable Organizational Commitment. The estimated value of this indicator is the largest among the other five indicators, which is 0.99.

➤ *Turnover intentions:*

Variable turnover intentions there are three indicators that affect the formation of variables, where all indicators are significant to measure variables. When viewed from the *estimatevalue onloadings* obtained for each indicator, the Y.2.3 indicator is the one that best describes the variable turnover intentions. The estimated value of this indicator is the largest among the other three indicators, which is 0.824.

Fig. 1: Structural Model

Table 2:

	Path coefficients					Keterangan
	Estimate	SE	95%CI(L)	95%CI(U)	HTMT	
Compensation->organizational commitment	0.802566	0.044662	0.702835	0.875288	0.8469204	signifikan
Komitmenorganisational->turnover intentions	0.584991	0.064966	0.441222	0.688995	0.9980579	signifikan
Intrinsic motivation->organizational commitment	-0.11208	0.07799	-0.23764	0.101501	0.2212198	signifikan
Compensation->turnover intentions	0.275717	0.22787	-0.18082	0.637597	1.0546992	Not signifikan
Intrinsic motivation->turnover intentions	-1.27164	1.204444	-0.6003	0.17449	0.0137706	signifikan

This table shows the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) per pair of components, i.e. defined as the mean value of the item correlation across the construction relative to the (geometric) average correlation for items measuring the same construct with a threshold value of 0.90 (Henseler, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2015).

➤ Information

- Compensation has a significant effect on organizational commitment and can be seen in the estimate value of 0.802566 and the HTMT value of 0.846 means that the hypothesis is accepted. This shows that compensation can increase organizational commitment. This study supports the research of I Gede Riana & I Wayan Pradnyantha Wirasedana, (2016) and found that compensation has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. This can mean that if employees receive compensation in accordance with their devotion and length of service, they will be committed to continuance and organization.
- Compensation has no significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimated value of 0.275717 and an HTMT value of 1.054. That is, the hypothesis is rejected. This shows that if lecturers receive minimal compensation, they feel less satisfied so they think about moving to teach to another private desert that provides proper compensation. This study is different from the research of Dzulfiqar Mudhoffar Siregar and Tri Maryati found that compensation has a significant effect on employees' desire to move to other organizations.
- Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment, meaning that the hypothesis is accepted. This can be seen from the estimated value of -0.11208 and the HTMT value of 0.221. This shows that if employees have high intrinsic motivation, organizational commitment is also high. In this regard, employees want to keep working in the organization. If the intrinsic motivation is high, then the employee is reluctant to leave the organization so do not think about moving to another organization. This study supports the research of Faisal N. Al-madi et al. (2017) found intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment (affective committee, continuance and normative). In addition, supporting Qëndrim Bytyqi's (2020) research found motivation has a significant effect on organizational commitment
- Organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimate value of 0.584991 and an HTMT value of 0.99. This means that the hypothesis is accepted. This can mean that if organizational commitment is high, it can minimize turnover intentions.

Belum adajurnalnya

- Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimate value of -1.27164 and an HTMT value of 0.013 meaning that the hypothesis is accepted. This shows that if intrinsic motivation is high, it can reduce the desire to move to another organization
- This research has no journal

VI. CONCLUSION

- Compensation has a significant effect on organizational commitment with an estimate value of 0.802566 and an HTMT value of 0.846 meaning that the hypothesis is accepted.
- Compensation has no significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimated value of 0.275717 and an HTMT value of 1.054.
- Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on commitment with an estimate value of -0.11208 and an HTMT value of 0.221.
- Organizational commitment has a significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimate value of 0.584991 and an HTMT value of 0.99.
- Intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on turnover intentions with an estimated value of -1.27164 and an HTMT value of 0.013.

VII. DISCUSSION

How do we know that the compensation received by lecturers can increase intrinsic motivation, and organizational commitment and minimize turnover intentions. However, in some cases private universities provide low compensation, which reduces organizational commitment and increases turnover intention. Andi Jemma University in Palopo Regency lecturers get salaries, functional allowances and family allowances, but are minimal because they are directly proportional to the number of students. Darma Nusantara Makassar College of Economics, foundation lecturers get salaries and functional allowances but are paid annually and there are no service classes. So if they teach three classes that pays three classes. In addition, lecturers with the functional position of associate professor are given awards to be dispatched for Umrah so that lecturers are motivated to take care of their functional promotions. Fajar University, and Nitro finance college before the covid-19 the salary of foundation lecturers was good because it was higher than the Provincial minimum wage standard and they were given functional allowances that were greater than the functional allowances of lecturers at State universities. In addition, lecturers are given food and transportation money as well as credit money. However, since the existence of COVID-19,

lecturers' functional allowances, food allowances, transportation fees and teaching fees have been reduced until now. Even though now the situation has improved, covid has gone from Bumi Indonesia, but the lecturers' compensation has not been stable. University of Eastern Indonesia lecturers do not get salaries and functional benefits to which they are entitled. They only get certification allowances for those who have passed certification. However, for those who have not passed the certification, they only get the honor of guiding the thesis and testing the thesis, but not every month there is a thesis exam. Lecturers who have structural positions such as Rector, dean and head of study programs who get a salary every month but are very minimal and do not get structural benefits. The lecturers' salaries are below the provincial minimum wage standard. The salary of workers in Makassar City is Rp 2,800,000, - While the lecturer of the University of East Indonesia foundation who serves as Dean and head of the study program has a salary lower than the provincial minimum wage. When compared the level of education of workers and lecturers is much different. Labor education is only high school graduates, while the majority of master's foundation lecturer education has even been educated a lot Dr. So lecturers should be rewarded with compensation higher than the provincial minimum wage. The lack of salary resulted in job dissatisfaction so that some foundation lecturers at several private universities moved to teach at other private universities because they were not satisfied with the compensation. Some moved to the Indonesian Muslim University, Bosowa Tas University, Darma Nusantara Makassar College of Economics and Amkop Makassar College of Economics.

VIII. LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH AND ADVICE

The limitation of this study is the lack of foundation lecturers who are willing to fill out questionnaires, this is evidenced by the questionnaires sent as many as 225 copies but only 98 questionnaires returned. In addition, there is limited time in research. It is recommended for private university managers/foundation chairmen and rectors to provide proper compensation and according to the level of education and functional positions of lecturers so that they are motivated to implement the tri darma of higher education and can increase organizational commitment so as to reduce turnover intentions. It is recommended that subsequent researchers examine compensation and it is associated with other variables such as job satisfaction and job involvement.

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